

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds. Part III : Synthesis of 3,5-diaryl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) Pyrazoles and Study of their Antibacterial Properties

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1-(*m*-Nitrophenyl)-3-phenyl-, and 1-(*m*-nitrophenyl)-3-(anisyl)-2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-diones on condensation with hydrazine hydrate (100%), phenylhydrazine, *p*-tolyl-hydrazine, and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine yield the respective 3-(*m*-nitrophenyl)-5-phenyl-, and 3-(*m*-nitrophenyl)-5-(anisyl)-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) pyrazoles. All these pyrazoles were found active when screened *in vitro* against two organisms *S. aureus* and *E. Coli*.

IN view of the encouraging results obtained during the course of our earlier work on the synthesis and screening of some aryl pyrazole derivatives¹, it was thought of interest to synthesise new pyrazole derivatives having electron attracting and/or repelling groups in the phenyl rings in order to study the effect of these groups on the antibacterial properties of these pyrazole derivatives.

The present paper describes the synthesis of 3-(*m*-nitrophenyl)-5-phenyl (substituted and 3-(*m*-nitrophenyl)-5-anisyl-4-sulphonamidobenzeneazo) pyrazoles of the

type A, which were obtained by condensing 1,3-diaryl-2-substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo), propane-1,3-diones with hydrazine hydrate (100%), phenylhydrazine, *p*-tolylhydrazine, and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine. The homogeneity of these compounds was tested by T. L. C. and the structure assigned on the basis of earlier work^{2,3}.

The antibacterial studies were carried out using cup-plate agar diffusion method and the results of screening at 500 µg/ml are entered in Tables I and 2.

TABLE I—3-(*m*-NITROPHENYL)-5-(*p*-METHOXYPHENYL)-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

S. No.	R	R ₁	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula	Percentage				Antibacterial activity, against	
							Found		Requires		S. aureus	E. coli
(A : X = <i>m</i> -Nitro ; Y = <i>p</i> -methoxy)							C	H	C	H		
1.	H	H	271-2	O	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₆ S	55.0	3.8	55.2	3.8	(-)	(++)
2.	"	Phenyl	257	OR	71	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₆ S	60.7	4.1	60.6	4.0	(+)	(++)
3.	"	<i>p</i> -Methyl phenyl	229	OR	63	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S	61.0	4.2	61.2	4.2	(-)	(+)
4.	"	<i>p</i> -Nitro phenyl	290	SR	72	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ O ₇ N ₇ S	56.2	3.4	56.1	3.5	(+)	(+)
5.	Acetyl	H	271-2	O	71	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₅ S	55.5	3.9	55.4	3.8	(-)	(+)
6.	"	Phenyl	224	OR	70	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₆ S	60.5	4.1	60.4	4.0	(-)	(++)
7.	"	<i>p</i> -Methyl phenyl	230	OR	62	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ O ₆ N ₆ S	61.1	4.1	60.9	4.2	(+)	(++)
8.	"	<i>p</i> -Nitro phenyl	288	BR	72	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ O ₈ N ₇ S	56.0	3.6	56.1	3.6	(+)	(++)
9.	Phenyl	H	211-2	O	65	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₆ S	60.5	4.1	60.6	4.0	(-)	(+)
10.	<i>p</i> -Chloro-Phenyl	H	219	O	67	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₆ SCl	57.2	3.5	57.1	3.6	(-)	(+)
11.	"	Phenyl	200-1	R	68	C ₃₄ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₆ SCl	61.4	3.9	61.4	3.8	(-)	(++)
12.	<i>p</i> -Methyl phenyl	H	210-1	YO	64	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S	61.2	4.3	61.2	4.2	(-)	(+)
13.	"	Phenyl	211-2	R	64	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₅ N ₆ S	65.3	4.3	65.2	4.3	(-)	(++)
14.	"	<i>p</i> -Methyl phenyl	195-6	R	54	C ₃₆ H ₃₀ O ₅ N ₆ S	65.8	4.4	65.6	4.5	(-)	(+)
15.	"	<i>p</i> -Nitro phenyl	271-2	R	63	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₇ S	61.1	4.0	60.9	3.9	(-)	(+)
16.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy phenyl	H	210	YO	67	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₆ S	59.7	4.0	59.6	4.1	(-)	(++)
17.	"	Phenyl	202	OR	67	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₆ N ₆ S	63.5	4.2	63.6	4.2	(-)	(++)
18.	"	<i>p</i> -Nitro phenyl	236	R	66	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₈ N ₇ S	59.5	3.8	59.5	3.7	(-)	(++)
19.	Pyrimidyl	H	293	SR	70	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₈ S	56.0	3.8	56.1	3.6	(-)	(+)
20.	"	Phenyl	237	O	69	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₈ S	60.7	4.0	60.7	3.8	(-)	(++)
21.	Guanidyl	H	268	LB	64	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₈ S	53.0	4.0	53.0	3.8	(-)	(+)
22.	"	<i>p</i> -Nitro phenyl	297	Y	72	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₈ S	49.1	4.0	48.9	4.1	(+)	(+)

O=Orange ; R=Red ; S=Shining ; B=Brown ; Y=Yellow ; L=Light ; N=Needles ; F=Flakes ; D=Dark

TABLE 2—3-(M-NITROPHENYL)-5-PHENYL-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

S. No.	R	R ₁	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula (A : X = <i>m</i> -Nitro ; Y = H)	Percentage				Antibacterial activity against	
							Found		Requires		S. aureus	E. coli
							C	H	C	H		
1.	H	H	228-9	YO	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₆ S	56.4	3.6	56.3	3.6	(—)	(+)
2.	„	Phenyl	147-8	ORN	76	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₆ S	61.6	3.9	61.8	3.8	(—)	(+)
3.	„	<i>p</i> -Methyl phenyl	192-3	R	64	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ S	62.6	3.9	62.4	4.0	(—)	(—)
4.	Acetyl	H	229	LO	74	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₆ S	56.3	3.4	56.3	3.6	(—)	(+)
5.	„	Phenyl	168-9	OF	75	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S	61.7	3.9	61.5	3.9	(+)	(++)
6.	„	<i>p</i> -Methyl phenyl	200	R	65	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S	62.1	4.3	62.0	4.1	(+)	(—)
7.	Phenyl	H	221	DOF	70	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₆ S	62.0	3.7	61.8	3.8	(—)	(++)
8.	<i>p</i> -Methyl phenyl	H	240	BOF	69	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ S	62.6	4.1	62.4	4.1	(—)	(+)
9.	„	Phenyl	211-2	B	68	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₆ S	66.5	4.3	66.5	4.3	(—)	(+)
10.	„	<i>p</i> -Methyl phenyl	210	R	54	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₆ S	67.0	4.3	66.8	4.4	(—)	(—)
11.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy phenyl	H	240	BO	70	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₆ S	60.8	4.1	60.7	4.0	(—)	(+)
12.	„	Phenyl	167-8	SR	71	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ O ₅ N ₆ S	65.0	3.9	64.8	3.9	(—)	(+)
13.	Pyrimidyl	H	251	O	73	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₆ S	57.1	3.5	57.0	3.4	(—)	(—)
14.	„	Phenyl	237	R	73	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ S	61.7	3.3	61.9	3.5	(++)	(++)

The results of antibacterial tests indicate that all the pyrazole derivatives, except compounds number 3, 6, 10 and 14 (Table 1), possess activity against *E. coli* and when tested against *S. aureus* majority of these were found inactive with the exception of few which showed very meagre activity.

The order of activity increases when the phenyl ring attached at position 3 carries the nitro group and the other at position 5 has the methoxyl group as compared to the compounds having the nitro group in the phenyl ring attached to position 3 of the pyrazole nucleus.

Another conclusion drawn has been that if any of the phenyl ring attached at position 1, 3, or 5 of the nucleus or N¹ of the sulphonamide residue carries an electron attracting group, the activity against *E. coli* was greater than those having an electron withdrawing group.

Experimental

1-(*p*-Nitrophenyl)-3, 5-diaryl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) pyrazoles: To a solution of

1, 3-diaryl-2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-dione (0.002 mole) in a mixture of glacial acetic acid and ethanol, *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine (0.003 mole) was added followed by a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid and the reaction mixture refluxed on a water bath for 8-9 hr. To the cooled solution few drops of water were added, the reaction mixture further refluxed for 2-3 hr and then left overnight. The solid which separated out was filtered, washed with ethanol, dried and crystallized from glacial acetic acid or from a mixture of DMF and ethanol.

Reactions with hydrazine hydrate (100%), phenylhydrazine and *p*-toluylhydrazine were carried out as reported in earlier communications^{1,4}.

References

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